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«Nýtask mér máltól».
Allusive Art and Exegetical Thought
in Einarr Skúlason's «Geisli»

Abstract: As recent studies have made increasingly clear, the Icelandic priest and court poet Einarr Skúlason (c. 1090-1160) played a pivotal role in the transition from the pre-literate to the learned phase of skaldic composition. Among the first skalds to actively engage with the poetic canon as an object of scholarly reflection, Einarr approached the old poets with an emulative intent, reviving the flourishing style that had distinguished the late pagan period of skaldic composition. His contribution to the history of *dróttkvæði* is especially evident in his stylistic renewal of the genre, most notably in *Geisli*, his panegyric for Saint Óláfr. Through a qualitative intertextual analysis, this article will illustrate how, in *Geisli*, the dialogue with the past is infused with theological resonances, revealing an allegorical and exegetical reading of the pre-Christian matter of traditional Norse poetry. Einarr's allusive art finds typological parallels in the techniques of the late-antique authors of Christian epics and conceptual parallels in contemporary theological reflections, thereby disclosing the doctrinal underpinnings of the thorough renovation of the skaldic genre in the course of the twelfth century.

Keywords: Einarr Skúlason, skaldic poetry, allusion, exegesis, theology

Riassunto: Studi recenti hanno reso sempre più chiaro il ruolo svolto dall'ecclesiastico e poeta di corte islandese Einarr Skúlason (c. 1090-1160) nel passaggio dalla fase preletteraria a quella erudita del genere scaldico. Tra i primi a dedicarsi ad uno studio sistematico del canone poetico volgare, questo autore diresse la propria attenzione alle più sofisticate tecniche retoriche dei suoi predecessori, replicandole in sistematici esercizi di *emulatio*. Così facendo, Einarr contribuì alla reintroduzione dello stile "barocco" che aveva caratterizzato la produzione scaldica della fase tardo-pagana. Nella storia del *dróttkvæði*, questa figura è altresì legata al rinnovamento stilistico del genere. Un sapiente connubio di novità e tradizione caratterizza, a tutti i livelli, il panegirico *Geisli*, dedicato a sant'Olaf. Una lettura intertestuale di quest'opera mette in luce varie allusioni agli scaldi del passato e le loro implicazioni teologiche, suggerendo un approccio esegetico ai miti pagani contenuti nella poesia norrena tradizionale. Le strategie allusive di *Geisli* ricordano le tecniche degli autori dell'epica cristiana di età tardo antica, mentre trovano paralleli concettuali nella produzione teologica contemporanea. Una loro analisi disvela, pertanto, i fondamenti dottrinali del processo che, nel corso del sec. XII, ha condotto a un rinnovamento profondo dell'arte scaldica.

Parole chiave: Einarr Skúlason, poesia scaldica, allusione, esegesi, teologia

1. Einarr Skúlason: A Janus Figure

The court poet and priest Einarr Skúlason (c. 1090-1160s) was hailed by Finnur Jónsson as the most significant and prolific skald of his century (*LH*, II: 62), a description which, among Old Norse philologists, Jón himself arguably merits. Einarr's magisterial panegyric, *Geisli* ('Beam of light'), composed in honor of the king and patron saint of Norway, Óláfr Haraldsson, is regarded as «a towering achievement [...] which opened the way for other Christian skalds to appropriate the courtliest forms of traditional verse for Christian purposes» (Abram 2014: 48). Einarr Skúlason was elevated by his kinsman, Snorri Sturluson, to an exemplary status in matters of poetic diction, as no other skald is cited more extensively in *Skáldskaparmál* (Guðrún Nordal 2001a: 76-77, 342). In fact, Einarr played a crucial role in the «gradual adoption of skaldic verse in an educational framework by the twelfth- and thirteenth-century élite» (Guðrún Nordal 2003: 4) and is now widely recognized as a key figure in the process whereby skaldic poetry «morphed from a living oral tradition into a literate, largely academic activity» (Abram 2014: 44).

This author's significance in the history of Old Norse poetry and poetics can thus hardly be overstated and, as recent research has increasingly made clear, it hinges on three principal aspects. Foremost among them is Einarr's role as an innovator who reformed the art of *dróttkvæði* from within, rearticulating the genre on Christian and learned foundations (Guðrún Nordal 2001a: 233, 337, 340-341). The second is his lasting influence on the later tradition and prominent place within the skaldic school canon (Wellendorf 2017). The last one concerns Einarr's part in giving impulse to the so-called "mythological renaissance", the learned interest in the mythological component of vernacular poetics that enabled the preservation and transmission of the pre-Christian poems and myths of the North (Guðrún Nordal 2001a: 337-342; Abram 2011: 196-198; Males 2020: 77-88). Einarr's oeuvre is thus characterized by a unique synthesis of tradition and innovation, most clearly expressed in his creative dialogue with the *fornskáld* ('ancient skalds') and their legacy. The present study addresses this thematic tension in Einarr's production, investigating both the literary strategies and the ideological implications underpinning this innovative poet's engagement with the skaldic tradition.

According to a mid-fourteenth century redaction of *Gunnlaugssaga ormstungu*, Einarr Skúlason belonged to the lineage of the *Mýramenn*, and is listed among the descendants of Egill Skallagrímsson, where, alongside Björn Hítðælakappi and Snorri Sturluson, he is described as one of the *skáldmenn miklir* ('great poets', *ÍF* 3: 51, n. 3)¹. He is tentatively identified as the son of Skúli Egilsson of Borg,

¹ Stockholm, Kungliga biblioteket, Holm perg 18 4to, fol. 12v, 15-16. The expression *Mýramenn* ('the people of Mýrar') is commonly used to designate the descendants of Skalla-Grímur Kveld-Úlfsson who settled in the region of Mýrar, with their main centre at Borg.

himself a descendant of Þórsteinn Egilsson. If this lineage is correct, it would make Einarr the brother of Þórðr Skúla-son, maternal grandfather of Snorri Sturluson (*SnE* III: 418; *ÍF* 2: 299-300, 303). Born around 1090 AD, Einarr Skúla-son was probably a young priest when he joined the retinue of King Sigurðr jórsala-fari's on the "Norwegian crusade" (c. 1107-1111), inaugurating an illustrious poetic career that would span approximately forty years (*SkP* 2: 538-542). In a list attributed to the Icelandic historiographer Ari Þorgilsson, dated around 1143, he is named among "some Icelandic highborn priests"². Nothing is known, however, about the youthful years of his ecclesiastical training:

Einarr's poetry shows that his education was extensive and thorough, but how and where he received it remains a mystery. He may have studied at one of the newly established Icelandic schools at Skálholt, Haukadahl or Oddi, or he may have followed in the footsteps of other prominent Icelanders of his time and traveled to Germany, France or England. What is clear is the depth and breadth of his learning. If it could be determined that Einarr did in fact study in Iceland, it would be a further indication that the schools of Iceland, even in their earliest days, were on a par with the best in Europe and England. (Chase 2003: 14)

According to *Skáldatal*, Einarr composed panegyrics for no fewer than eight Norwegian rulers, spanning from the Magnússynir, Eysteinn and Sigurðr jórsala-fari (r. 1103-1130) to the three Haraldssynir: Ingi, Sigurður and Eysteinn (1150s). Under the latter, he was appointed *stallari* ('king's marshal'). He also dedicated poems to the Norwegian magnates Grégórius Dagsson and Eindriði ungi, King Sörkvir Kolsson of Sweden and his son Jón jarl Sörkvisson, as well as the Danish king Sveinn sviðandi Eiríksson (*SnE* III: 252-286; *SkP* 2: 140). Toward the end of his career, Einarr delivered his masterpiece, *Geisli*, possibly for the feast of Saint Óláfr in the newly established metropolitan see of Níðaróss, in July 1153. *Geisli* represents a watershed moment in skaldic production. The first *drápa* transmitted in its entirety, this work embodies a subtle synthesis of traditional Old Norse *dróttkvæði* conventions and European religious poetry, heralding in grand style the dawn of a new era in skaldic poetics (Chase 2003; Abram 2004a: 21-27). Thus, Einarr emerges as a Janus figure, looking backward and forward simultaneously. By rekindling traditional mythological diction while, at the same time, securing skaldic poetry a place within the schools, he bridged the gap between past and present, pagan lore and Christian learning, transposing the poetic traditions of the pre-literate skalds into the practice of medieval scholars (Guðrún Nordal 2003). While inaugurating a new poetic style, Einarr drew inspiration from the past, selectively isolating models from the traditional canon. His engagement with tradition appears to have been twofold: on the formal level, he meticulously studied

² Reykjavík, Stofnun Árna Magnússonar í íslenskum fræðum, GKS 1812 4to, 5ra, 1-15.

the stylistic feats of the ancient poets, mastering and replicating their techniques, in a dynamic of *imitatio* and *emulatio*. On a content level, his dialogue with the vernacular tradition takes, at times, the more subtle form of *oppositio in imitando* (Farrell 1991: 13), where implicit poetic allusions serve as vehicles for implications that extend beyond the purely poetic discourse.

By means of a qualitative intertextual analysis of selected passages, this article will examine various instances of Einarr's re-elaboration of canonical passages, looking in particular at instances of "allusive art" (Pasquali 2003), targeting pagan skalds of the ninth and tenth centuries. A close reading will reveal instances of various intertextual strategies, such as "paradiorthosis" or imperfect quotation (Frye *et al.* 1985: 334) and *Kontrastimitation* (Green 2006: 63). The study further explores the theological implications of these allusive acts, revealing interpretative mechanisms typical of twelfth-century exegetical doctrines, such as the so-called "Augustinian chiasm" (Satran 2004). This study is thus able to disclose both the literary and the theological underpinnings of Einarr's operation, shedding light on the intellectual framework which produced the twelfth-century renovation of skaldic poetics.

2. Emulating the Tenth-Century Masters

Over the five centuries of its development, trends in skaldic style were largely determined by evolving attitudes towards the pre-Christian matter contained in kennings, reflecting the religious and cultural climate in Norway and Iceland³. Following a genuinely pagan phase (*c.* 850-1000), and the "long eleventh-century" of the early Christianization, during which pagan imagery was mostly eschewed (*c.* 1020-1130s), it is precisely the work of Einarr Skúlason that recent scholarship identifies as the beginning of the antiquarian or learned phase of skaldic stylistics, often referred to as "mythological renaissance". In the course of the twelfth century, pre-Christian lore, now stripped of any religious significance, was revived as a rhetorical ornament, informed by the study of classical mythology as prescribed by late antique and medieval grammarians (Guðrún Nordal 2001a: 35, 341; Wellendorf 2016: 142-143; 2017: 125). Pagan mythology thus reemerges through the filter of European education, as a paradoxical product of Christian learning. Mythologizing diction no longer graces courtly panegyrics, however, but is primarily found in backward-looking poems recounting tales from the past or in what appear to have been schoolroom exercises. A notable example of this didactic approach is the series of fragments attributed to Einarr Skúlason in *Skáldskaparmál*,

³ On this topic, see the studies by: Vries (1934); Fidjestøl (1993: 270-293); Abram (2014); Males (2017); (2019); (2020: 39-101).

containing the description of a precious weapon, known editorially as *Øxarflokkur* ('Poem about an Axe', *SnE* III: 364-365). This poem reveals a clear antiquarian agenda, showcasing rare kennings and numerous references to both major pagan deities and minor mythological figures. The splendid weapon, adorned with silver and gold, is compared to Freyja's daughter, the goddess Hnoss, through a double entendre that plays on the literal meaning of her name (ON *hnoss* 'treasure'). This poetic device enables a personification of the axe, which is thus compared to a divine female figure, entering the skald's possession:

Gaf, sás erring ofrar,
 ógnprúðr Vana brúðar
 þing- Váfaðar -þrøngvir
 þróttöflga mér dóttur.
 Ríkr leiddi mey mækis
 mótvaldr á beð skaldi
 Gefnar glóðum drifna
 Gautreks svana brautar.
 (*Øxarflokkur* 5, ed. by K.E. Gade, *SkP* 3: 145)

[The battle-proud compeller of the assembly of Váfuðr [ÓÐINN > BATTLE > WARRIOR], who displays courage, gave me the mightily strong daughter of the Vanir's bride [FREYJA > HNOSS > TREASURE]. The powerful ruler of the meeting of the sword [BATTLE > WARRIOR] led the maiden of Gefn [FREYJA > HNOSS > TREASURE], covered with embers of the road of Gautrekr's swans [SEA-KING > SWANS > SEA > GOLD], to the poet's bed.]⁴

In this stanza, a *double-face* portrayal emerges through a semantic harmonization of kenning base-words and verbs, a technique known as "sentence metaphor" (Lie 1982: 259; Patria 2022: 129-132). The verbs selected to describe the act of gift-giving carry erotic nuances, which become overt when the goddess-figure, symbolizing the treasure, is "led to the skald's bed". The revival of mythological diction and intricate metaphorical imagery was mediated by a careful emulation of earlier poets, and nowhere is Einarr's *modus operandi* more apparent than in the comparison between *Øxarflokkur* and its direct tenth-century model, Hallfreðr vandræðaskáld's *Hákonadrápa* (Males 2020: 82). In this poem, a strikingly similar combination of wordplay, personification and extended metaphors grounded in erotic imagery characterizes the description of Hákon jarl's seduction of the goddess Jorð (ON *jorð* 'earth, land'), Óðinn's mistress:

⁴ Most translations of skaldic verse are based on the ones provided by the cited editors in the reference edition, but I have often made slight adaptations. Major deviations from their readings will be signalled in the notes. Prose translations are mine, unless otherwise stated.

Róð lukusk, at sá síðan
 snjallráðr konungs spjalli
 átti eingadóttur
 Ónars viði gróna.
 (*Hákonardrápa* 7, ed. K. Heslop, *SkP* 3: 223)

[The marriage was concluded, so that shrewdly-advising king's intimate [HÁKON JARL] afterward possessed the only daughter of Ónarr [JØRD > EARTH/LAND], overgrown with forest.]

While in Hallfreðr's poem the seduction of the divine bride conveys a powerful political message (the seduction of the land-goddess being a transparent allegory for the acquisition of Hákon's lordship over Norway), Einarr's elaborated metaphors, by contrast, verge on the ornamental, culminating somewhat clumsily in the image of the poet taking his glittering "new toy" to bed, like a child indulging in a cherished gift on Christmas Eve. Evidently, the poet's interest lay on form rather than message: Einarr aimed at surpassing Hallfreðr's metaphorical technique, mythological imagery, and lexical ingenuity. Like heavily mythologizing diction, sentence metaphor was a hallmark of late pagan verse, a style that became rare during the eleventh century; poems such as Hallfreðr's *Hákonardrápa* testify to the high degree of experimentation with kenning language achieved in the late tenth century. As the following example will illustrate, the sophisticated diction of the skalds of this period was target of Einarr's systematic imitations.

3. On the Track of Gísli Súrsson

In a fragment of *Skáldskaparmál* preserved only in the Codex Wormianus (*Orms-Eddu-brot*), a single *helmingr* is cited to illustrate the rare kenning *hausmjöll* ('the skull's powder-snow'). The first two lines of this fragment are also found in manuscripts of the seventeenth-century redaction known as *Laufás-Edda*. In all versions the poet is identified as just "Einarr", which typically refers to Einarr Skúlason in *Skáldskaparmál* (*SkP* 3: 175). The *helmingr* appears to belong to a stanza describing a woman and reveals a particular attention on sentence-metaphor techniques. Once the *kenningar* are correctly interpreted, the four lines describe the "cascade" of the lady's bright hair, while the choice of verbs and kenning base-words conjures up the imagery of a snowfall blanketing a pristine mountain landscape:

Hrynja lét in hvíta
 hausmjöll ofan lausa

strind aurriða strandar
 stalls af svarðar fjalli.
 (Einarr Skúlason, *lv* 12, ed. K.E. Gade, *SkP* 3: 175)

[The white land of the resting-place of the trout of the beach [SERPENT > GOLD > WOMAN] let the skull's fine snow [HAIR] fall loose down from the mountain of the scalp [HEAD]]⁵.

The *helmingr* is notable not only for its rare kennings and for the finely crafted sentence metaphor, but also for a deliberate intertextual allusion to a tenth-century stanza. The first line, *hrynja lét in hvíta*, echoes the opening of a *lausavísa* attributed to Gísli Súrsson, the tenth-century outlaw and poet, hero of the eponymous *Gísla saga Súrssonar*:

Hrynja lætr af hvítum
 hvarmskógi Gnó bógar
 hrönn; fylvingum hyljar
 hlátrbann í kné svanna.
 Hnetr less, en þreyr þessum,
 Þögn, at mærdar Rögni,
 snákatúns af sínu
 sjónhesli þögrónu.
 (Gísli Súrsson, *lv* 5, ed. K.E. Gade, *SkP* 3: 557)

[The Gná of the arm [GODDESS > WOMAN] lets a wave fall from the white eyelid-forest [EYELASHES]; laughter-prohibition [SORROW] makes it rain nuts onto the woman's lap. The Þögn [GODDESS] of the snake-yard [GOLD > WOMAN]) gathers nuts from her hazel-wood of sight [EYELASHES], overgrown with grief, and longs for this Rögni of praise [ÓÐINN > POET = GÍSLI]].

The woman depicted in this *vísa* is not letting her fine hair cascade, but rather a stream of tears. According to the saga, the lines describe Gísli's wife, Auðr, mourning the death of her brother (*ÍF* 6: 46-48). A sustained metaphor runs through the stanza, where tears are likened to nuts falling and being gathered from the "branches" of Auðr's eyelashes. Based on metrical and linguistic evidence, the *vísa* can be dated to the lifetime of the historical Gísli (c. 960s), likely forming part to the saga's older poetic layer (Myrvoll 2020: 249). The subtle yet significant parallel between the two opening lines of Gísli's and Einarr's stanzas is achieved through the technique of paradiorthosis, or

⁵ The last two words of the *helmingr* are supplied by conjecture. *Fjall* is partly secured by rhyme; the preceding word should be a determinant for "head"; the form *svarðar*, proposed by Kari Ellen Gade, satisfies meaning and meter and occurs in the prose commentary that precedes the poetic quotation.

inexact quotation, in which a recognizable phrase or line is borrowed «without acknowledgement and with a new context or twist» (Frye *et al.* 1985: 334). In the commentary to *Háttatal*, Snorri refers to this phenomenon as a poetic license, namely that of appropriating another poet's words while limiting the echo to "one poetic line or less", by means of minimal modifications (Faulkes 2007: 8; Patria 2025).

Gísli Súrsson, *lv* 5, l. 1
Hrynja lætr af hvítum

Einarr Skúlason, *lv* 12, l. 1
Hrynja lét in hvíta

This technique is typical of skaldic poetics and usually signals a deliberate allusion to a previous work. Since the recognizability of the source is central to paradiorthoseis, the echo often focuses on the first line, the most memorable segment of a skaldic stanza. Gísli's *vísa* is remarkable for its use of kennings and metaphors, so that the lifting of its first line likely serves to highlight Einarr's demanding emulative exercise⁶. Indeed, the striking imagery of Gísli's stanza seems to have piqued the interest of another scholar interested in skaldic poetics: the anonymous author of the brief treatise on kennings known as *Litla Skálda* (Finnur Jónsson 1931: 255-259). This author glosses the rare word *fylving* with *hmetr*, arguably on the basis of Gísli's *vísa* (Solvin 2015: 75). Thus, the gloss in *Litla Skálda* and Einarr Skúlason's imitation concur with formal criteria in bolstering the case for the authenticity of this *lausavísa*. Despite Snorri's silence about him, Gísli's poetry thus appears to have held canonical status, being known and studied in twelfth-century Iceland. The cases of imitation presented so far focused solely on the formal aspects of the models. I will now turn to more nuanced instances of allusion, where the *contents* of the source-texts hold deeper implications for the poet and his audience. In fact, a more subtle dialogue with the skaldic tradition unfolds in Einarr Skúlason's most renowned and celebrated poem, the hagiographical panegyric *Geisli*.

4. Tradition and Innovation in *Geisli*

The composition of *Geisli* is frequently cited as a turning point in the evolution of skaldic poetics, as this *drápa* exemplifies a harmonious fusion of ancient forms and new meanings, evident in its structural design, themes and diction (Attwood 1994; Chase 2003; Abram 2004a). The first two stanzas aptly illustrate the degree of theological and poetic sophistication of Einarr's operation, seamlessly combining foreign tropes and local conventions:

⁶ *Litla Skálda* has been argued to be older than *Skáldskaparmál* (Solvin 2015; Males 2020: 129-140); on the basis of lexical correspondences between its content and the kennings of *Háttalykill*, Judith Jesch has suggested a late-twelfth century Orcadian context of composition (2009: 153-159).

Eins má óð ok bænir
 – alls ráðanda ins snjalla
 vels fróðr, sás getr góða –
 Guðs þrenning mér kenna.
 Gøfugt ljós boðar geisli
 gunnøflugr miskunnar
 – ágætan býðk ítrum
 Óláfi brag – sólar,

[The Trinity of one God can teach me poetry and prayers; he is indeed wise who gets the goodwill of the eloquent ruler of all [GOD]. The battle-strong light beam of the sun of mercy [GOD > ÓLÁFR] – I offer the excellent poem to glorious Óláfr – proclaims the splendid light...]

þeirars heims (í heimi)
 (heims) myrkur brá (þeima)
 ok (ljós meðan) var vísi
 veðr- (kallaðisk) -hallar.
 Sá lét bjartr frá bjartri
 berask maðr und skýjaðri
 (frægr stóð af því) flæðar
 (fornuðr) røðull stjörnu.
 (*Geisli*, 1-2, ed. M. Chase, *SkP* 7: 7-9)

[... of that [sun] which destroyed the darkness of the world and was the prince of the wind-hall [SKY > CHRIST]), while he called himself the light of the world in this world. That bright sun [CHRIST] caused himself to be born as a man from the bright star of the sea [MARY] under the cloud-rim [SKY]; renowned prosperity proceeded from that.]

Despite the presence of skaldic figures such as tmesis, interlaced syntax and retained rhyme schemes, the diction of these stanzas is more deeply rooted in Christian tropes than in traditional skaldic poetics. Several of the images and kennings are directly derived from Latin hymnology or patristic topoi. The overarching metaphor of Saint Óláfr as a light beam emanating from Christ, the divine “sun of mercy” (*miskunnar sól*, st. 1), is an unusual notion, carrying both theological and typological implications, but it does find parallels in the light imagery of Ambrosian hymns (Chase 2003: 19-25). In *Geisli*, for the first time in skaldic diction, the *Lichtmotivik* typical of medieval Christian poetry (Röttger 1996) uses celestial imagery to create a suggestive play of lights throughout the poem⁷. The similarly unprecedented kenning *flæðar stjörn* (‘star of the flood/sea’, st. 2, ll. 7-8) is a calque on the Marian title *stella maris*, attested in the ninth-century hymn

⁷ See, for instance, sts 2, 3, 19, 67 (*SkP* 7: 8-9; 22-23; 61-62).

Ave maris stella (Chase, *SkP* 7: 8). The combination of polyptoton and retained rhyme produces the effect known as *iðurmælt* ('repetition'), in Snorri's terminology (Faulkes 2007: 22). This figure, featuring prominently in the opening stanzas (st. 2, ll. 1-2: *þeirars heims í heimi | heims myrkrum brá þeima*; st. 2, l. 5: *sá lét bjartr frá bjartri*), carries, and enhances, Scriptural echoes:

The repetition of *heims / heimi / heims* is also an echo of the prologue to the Gospel of John: *erat lux vera quae inluminat omnem hominem venientem in mundum / in mundo erat et mundus per ipsum factus est et mundus eum non cognovit* 'That was the true light, which enlighteneth every man that cometh into this world. He was in the world: and the world was made by him: and the world knew him not' (John I. 9-10). The Bb reading *bjartr frá bjartri* (l. 5) follows a similar pattern and echoes the *lumen de lumine* 'light from light' of the *Credo*. (Chase, *SkP* 7: 8-9)

In the poem's opening lines, liturgical resonances are thus interwoven with the traditional courtly form, offering «the first hint of the richness accessible to poets through a blending of traditional style, Biblical imagery, aspects of Latin hymnody, and an exemplary Christian subject» (Abram 2014: 48). *Geisli* is also the first *drápa* to make use of kennings that describe God by means of devotional and abstract attributes. In the eleventh century, skalds primarily referred to God and Christ by adapting established "ruler" kennings, sometimes creating unintentionally humorous expressions like *munka dróttinn* ('leader of monks') or *Jórðánar gramr* ('prince of the [river] Jordan')⁸. In the mid-twelfth century, kennings begin to acquire religious poignancy, exploring a more strictly theological characterization of God (Males 2019: 153-158). It is specifically in *Geisli* that we find for the first time kennings such as *dýrðar dróttinn* ('lord of glory', st. 6, l. 1, *SkP* 7: 11), *ítr græðari alls* ('glorious healer of all', st. 21, ll. 3-4, *SkP* 7: 24), *heims lækni* ('healer of the world', st. 57, l. 8, *SkP* 7: 53) or *heims dómari* ('judge of the world', st. 42, l. 2, *SkP* 7: 42). Einarr is thus thoroughly renovating the language of praise by introducing foreign tropes as well as by venturing into the as yet unexplored territory of abstract and devotional kennings.

In addition to these innovations, scholars have noted intertextual connections to older, and often pagan, poems (Weber 1997; Guðrún Nordal 2001a: 342). The rest of this article will illustrate three instances of this phenomenon, arguing that they represent a deliberate appropriation of the source-text intended for recognition by a learned audience. While previous research has identified two such cases of re-semanticization within the skaldic tradition, their full implications remain underexplored. As far as I am aware, the third instance has not been noticed previously. In these case-studies, allusions to paganism are imbued with new meaning

⁸ The two kennings are found, respectively, in Skapti Þóroddsson's *Fragment 1* (*SkP* 3: 356) and in Sighvatr Þórðarson's *Erfidrápa Óláfs helga* st. 28 (*SkP* 1: 697).

within a Christian framework, exemplifying Einarr's subtle adaptive strategy. This intertextual dynamic extends beyond mere poetic technique, carrying theological implications akin to the typological and allegorical readings proper of exegetical practice.

5. Converting the Tradition

Males identified the first instance of paradiorthosis in *Geisli*, drawing attention to Einarr Skúlaason's general stylistic preference for the poetry of Hallfreðr vandræðaskáld (2020: 80-84). The allusion appears in a passage of *Geisli* describing Saint Óláfr's death, where a solar eclipse obscures the sky, and the poet directly points out that a similar event occurred during Christ's crucifixion:

Náðit bjartr, þás beiðir
 baugskjalda lauk aldri
 – sýndi salvörðr grundar
 sín tókn – røðull skína.
 Fyrr vas hitt, at harra
 hauðrtjalda brá dauða
 happ- (nýtask mér) -mætu
 (máltól) skini sólar.
 (*Geisli* 16, ed. M. Chase, *SkP* 7: 42-43)

[The bright sun was unable to shine when the desirer of ring-shields [WARRIOR = ÓLÁFR] ended his life; the guardian of the hall of earth [SKY > GOD] showed his signs. *It was in the past that* the excellent, fortunate shining of the sun ceased through the death of the *lord* of earth-tents [SKY > CHRIST]; speech-tools are of use to me.]

Males observed a notable similarity between line 5 (in italics above) and the opening line of a *helmingr* attributed to Hallfreðr vandræðaskáld, belonging to his renowned “conversion stanzas” (2020: 82). Hallfreðr, formerly a court poet of the pagan Hákon jarl, later entered the retinue of the Christian Óláfr Tryggvason. These verses reflect a professional reluctance to abandon the pagan gods, who had been so beneficial to his skaldic activity (Wood 1935; Poole 2002; Goeres 2011). The *helmingr* in question evokes memories of offering sacrifices to Óðinn, the god of poetry:

Fyrr vas hitt, es harra
 Hliðskjalfar gat'k sjalfan,
 – skipt es á gumna giptu –
 geðskjótan vel blóta.
 (Hallfreðr vandræðaskáld, *lv* 6, ed. D. Whaley, *SkP* 5: 883)

[*It was in the past that I could sacrifice well to Hliðskjölf's quick-minded lord himself [ÓÐINN]. There has been a change in the fortune of men.*]

The aural resonance between the two texts is enhanced by the fact that, while the first line remains nearly unchanged, the following line diverges in wording but maintains an identical metrical structure (a type-D line with a compound in positions 1-3 followed by the syntactical caesura: $\bar{-} \bar{x} | x \bar{-} x$):

Hallfreðr, *lv* 6, ll. 1-2

Fyrr vas hitt, es harra
Hliðskjalfar gat'k sjalfan

Geisli, st. 16, ll. 5-6

Fyrr vas hitt, at harra
hauðrtjalda brá dauða

The reworking hinges on the term *harri* ('lord'): in Hallfreðr's stanza, it refers to Óðinn, 'the quick-minded lord of Hliðskjölf' (*Hliðskjalfar geðskjótr harri*)⁹. In *Geisli*, *harri* becomes the base-word of a kenning for Christ, *hauðrtjalda harri* 'lord of the tents of the earth', signifying 'lord of the sky vault, lord of heavens'. While the juxtaposition of the old and new "lord" remains implicit, the close echo likely resonated with a skaldic-educated audience¹⁰. The old kenning is thus appropriated and redirected to designate the true object of worship, thereby diminishing the pagan god's stature by comparison. This technique evokes appropriation strategies employed by late antique authors of early Christian epics, such as Juvencus and Sedulius. A particularly similar trope is the so-called *Kontrastimitation* (Thraede 1962; Green 2006: 63), «whereby an allusion to pagan literature is redirected to suggest a point of contrast with the Christian text. In this case, and ironically, the epic language serves to promote the greater status of God and his omnipotence over pagan deities» (McBrine 2017: 36). Although the extent to which the pagan text's echo contributes to the Christian text's meaning can be ambiguous, *Kontrastimitation* often entails exegetical readings (Green 2007: 2). Strikingly, in this instance, one of the rare overt references to pagan sacrifices (expressed by the verb *blóta*) is repurposed within a stanza depicting Christ's sacrifice on the Cross: the divine sacrifice that superseded all others.

Einar's deliberate allusion is underscored by the interlaced meta-poetic declaration: *nýtask mér máltól* ('tools of speech are of use to me'), arguably alluding to the intertextual operation at play. *Geisli*'s unprecedented level of meta-literary presence marks its adherence to the conventions of late antique and medieval religious poetic conventions, through innovative and foreign textual features. This is evident in the programmatic statements contained within the poem's paratextual

⁹ According to *Gylfaginning*, this is the name of Óðinn's high-seat or watchtower, from where he can visually dominate the entire world (Faulkes 2005: 13).

¹⁰ It may be noted that, as in the case of Gísli's stanza before, Einar's paradiorthosis lends credibility to his source's claim to authenticity and popularity.

sections (*upphaf* and *slæmr*), which introduce several Christian tropes previously unattested in skaldic verse (Fidjestøl 1991; Abram 2004a; Patria, forthcoming)¹¹. The allusion to Hallfreðr's stanza, which questions the inherent relationship between paganism and the skaldic art, suggests strong meta-poetic awareness. This is somewhat reminiscent of the «tongue-in-cheek rejection of traditional skaldic topoi» that Jonas Wellendorf (2016: 131) convincingly described in the opening of *Jómsvíkingadrápa*, composed just a few decades later by the bishop of Orkney, Bjarni Kolbeinsson. Bjarni expressed his learned and ironic attitude towards pagan diction by means of a similar intertextual strategy of *oppositio in imitando*, that combined Odinic imagery and an Ovidian topos. While the topic of Bjarni's poem was mundane, however, treating the loves and battles of the “picaresque” Jómsvíkingar, the occurrence of an allusion to Óðinn in the hagiographical *Geisli* seems to suggest a stronger religious tension. Indeed, scholars have identified a comparable tension within another poetic allusion in *Geisli*.

6. Mythological Kennings and “Skaldic Exegesis”

In *Geisli*, sts 43 and 50 recount miracles associated with Saint Óláfr's sword, Hneitir. The stanza introducing this miraculous weapon extends the sun metaphor, typically connecting Christ to Ólafr, to the saint's sword. This connection is amplified through a sentence-metaphor, depicting Óláfr's sword as a light beam piercing the clouds of his enemies' shields (highlighted below):

Hneitir, frá k, at héti,
 hjaldrs at vápna galdri,
 Óláfs hjorr, þess's orra
 ilbleikum gaf steikar.
Þeim klauf þengill Rauma
þunnvaxin ský gunnar
 – rekin bitu stól – á Stikla-
 stöðum valbatar róðli.
 (*Geisli* 43, ed. M. Chase, *SkP* 7: 42-43)

[I heard that the sword of Óláfr, who gave meat to the pale-footed black grouse of battle [RAVEN] at the chant of weapons [BATTLE], was called Hneitir. With that sun

¹¹ In *Geisli*, several elements of Christian meta-poetics are attested for the first time: the prayer for divine inspiration (ultimately a Christian re-elaboration of classical proemial topoi); ineffability, humility and *Quellenberufung* topoi; the meta-textual introduction of the poem's refrain in st. 18 (*SkP* 7: 21-22), later imitated and canonized in other religious *drápur* from the late twelfth century (*Placítusdrápa* st. 11; *Rekstefja* st. 24; *Harmsól* st. 20; *Leiðarvisan* st. 13).

of the sword-hilt [SWORD] the king of the Raumar [ÓLÁFR] clove the thin-grown clouds of battle [SHIELD] at Stiklestad; inlaid steel weapons bit.]¹²

Upon Óláfr's death in battle, a Swedish Varangian seizes his sword. Hneitir thus finds its way into the hands of soldiers serving in the Byzantine army (st. 44, *SkP* 7: 43-44), where the sword's miraculous nature becomes evident, as it mysteriously moves of its own accord for three consecutive nights. Ultimately, the emperor of Constantinople himself acquires the sword and venerates it as a relic.

Mós frá k jarðar eisu
 alls vald fyr hjör gjalda,
 (sléttik óð) þanns átti
 Óláfr (bragar tólum).
 Yfirskjöldungur lét jöfra
 oddhríðar þar síðan
 garðs of golli vörðu
 grand altári standa.
 (*Geisli* 50, ed. M. Chase, *SkP* 7: 48)

[I heard [that] the ruler of all [BYZANTINE EMPEROR] paid with the fire of the seagull's land [SEA > GOLD] for the sword which Óláfr had owned – I smooth [my] poem with the tools of poetry [ORGANS OF SPEECH]. The supreme king of princes [BYZANTINE EMPEROR] then caused the harm of the yard of the point-storm [BATTLE > SHIELD > SWORD] to stand there over the altar adorned with gold.]

It was a simple soldier, however, who first observed Hneitir's miraculous nature. Waking up one morning after having decided to sleep *à la belle étoile* girded with the sword (st. 47, *SkP* 7: 45-46), the baffled soldier discovered the weapon on the ground, some distance away from its original location:

Nýtr gat séð á slétri
 seimþiggjandi liggja
 grundu gylðis kindar
 gómsparra sér fjarri.
 (*Geisli* 48, ed. M. Chase, *SkP* 7: 46-47)

[The useful gold-receiver [SOLDIER] was able to see the gum-spar of the wolf's offspring [SWORD] lying far from him on the flat ground.]

While the entity of the miracles of the somnambulant Hneitir may appear somewhat modest, the kenning used for the sword in this stanza is truly remarkable:

¹² Einarr Skúlason, *Geisli*, st. 43, ed. by Martin Chase (*SkP* 7: 42-43), my emphasis.

gylðis kindar gómsparra ('the gum-spar of the wolf's offspring', i.e. 'the gum-spar of Fenrir')¹³. This kenning alludes to a pagan myth recounted by Snorri in *Gylfaginning*: when the Æsir bound the monstrous wolf Fenrir, they secured him with chains and stuck a sword into his gaping mouth as a brace, to prevent him from devouring them (see: Appendix, figure 1):

Úlfrinn gapði ákafliga ok feksk um mjök ok vildi bíta þá. Þeir skutu í munn honum sverði nokkvoru; nema hjóltin við neðra gómi, en efra gómi blóðrefill. Þat er gómsparri hans. Han grenjar illiliga ok slefa renn ór munni hans. Þat er á sú er Ván heitir. Þar liggr hann til raganrøkr. (Faulkes 2005: 29)

[The wolf gaped vigorously, became furious and wanted to bite them. They threw a sword in his mouth, so that the hilt got stuck in the inferior gum and the blade-point in the superior one. That is his "gum-spar". He roars horribly and drool runs from his mouth. That is the river called Ván. He lies there [like this] until *ragnarøkkr*.]

Snorri likely had the *Geisli* kenning in mind when noting that "this is the wolf's *gómsparri*", a term otherwise unattested. Indeed, the kenning-pattern is extremely rare: the only other instance occurs in a *lausavísa* by Eyvindr skáldaspillir, dated to c. 962: *Fenris varra sparri* 'the spar of Fenrir's lips' (Males 2020: 85)¹⁴. These unique kennings suggest that, as in the previously examined examples, Einarr may have not only drawn inspiration from Eyvindr but also subtly alluded to his heavily mythologizing and pagan production. The principal skald of Hákon góði, Eyvindr composed for him the distinctly Odinic funerary poem *Hákonarmál* and, after the king's death, joined the poetic circle of Hákon jarl in Hlaðir. Eyvindr seems to have been fond of the myth of Fenrir's binding; in an adynaton figure celebrating Hákon góði's unparalleled greatness, he again references the unbound Fenrir, whose return will signal the beginning of the end of the world:

Mun óbundinn á ýta sjöt
Fenrisulfr fara,
áðr jafngóðr á auða tröð
konungmaðr komi. (*Hákonarmál* 20, ed. R. Fulk, *SkP* 1: 192)

[The wolf Fenrir will wander, unbound, across the dwelling of men, before an equally good king comes onto the deserted land].

¹³ The expression *gylðis kindar* (gen. 'of the wolf's offspring') contains a further echo of the expression *Fenris kindir* ('the offspring of Fenrir') occurring in the eschatological eddic poem *Völuspá* (st. 40, *Edda*: 9).

¹⁴ Eyvindr skáldaspillir, *lausavísa* 7, ll. 1-2: *Fyrr rauð Fenris varra | flugvarr konungr sparra* ('Earlier on, the flight-reluctant king reddened the spar of the lips of Fenrir [SWORD]'), ed. R. Poole (*SkP* 1: 223).

Weber (1997) and Males (2020) have both highlighted the religious implications of Einarr Skúlason's adaptation, arguing that the pagan eschatological symbolism associated with the beast Fenrir must be considered when interpreting the kenning's Christian re-purposing:

The kenning *gylðis kindar gómsparri* refers to the instrument which incapacitated an eschatological beast [the wolf Fenrir] until the last days, and by using it for [Saint] Óláfr's sword, Einarr lets that relic serve as a symbol of faith, or even Christ, neutralizing the destructive force of the Devil until the final battle comes. Just like in the case of *harri*, he has appropriated a pagan motif and in a sophisticated way turned it into a Christian purpose (Males 2020: 86).

Males further observes how Einarr's strategy is reminiscent of other cases of Christian typological re-interpretation of mythical narratives. Although the *gómsparri* kenning lacks a direct textual parallel in Christian literature, «Michael's and Christ's defeat of the Devil seem to be a likely point of reference» (2020: 86). In fact, a vernacular sermon about superstition contained in *Hauksbók* (AM 554 4to, 9v-10v) and possibly dated to the late twelfth-century, offers corroborating evidence in the following passage:

Vér skulum vár vel gæta með djöfuls svikum ok svá oss vandlega signa með Guðs pinslar marki, en þat er kross dróttins várs. Vér skulum gera hann á oss með rétri trú, ok láta oss þann kross þá í hug koma er dróttinn vár var pindr á; þá er fjándinn hræddari við hann heldr enn við ekki vápn annað, hvárki sverð nema æxi, fyrir því at þá er vár dróttinn herjaði í helvíti, ok batt djöfulinn, *þá setti hann kross í munn honum ok kom með því yfir hann*, ok bauð oss með því sigrmarki at verja djöflum ok illum vættum (Jón Þorkelsson 1865: 32, my emphasis).

[We shall well guard ourselves against the devil's deceits, and so diligently sign ourselves with the mark of God's pains, and that is the cross of our Lord. We shall make it on ourselves with right faith, and let come to our mind that cross on which our Lord was tortured upon, because the devil is more afraid of it than any other weapon, be it sword or axe. Because, when our Lord harrowed Hell and bound the devil, *He set the cross in his mouth, and thus overcame him*, and He commanded us to defend [ourselves] with that sign of victory against devils and all evil creatures.]

The text is often identified with the words of the partially illegible rubric, “*Hér segir...*” and is an adaptation of Ælfric's *Sermo in laetania maiore* (also known as *De Augustinis*), in turn indebted to several sources, among them a pseudo-Augustinian text ascribed to Caesarius of Arles (Meaney 1985; Frankis 2016: 69-80)¹⁵.

¹⁵ This explains the attribution to “Augustinus byskup” in the opening of the Old Norse text (AM 544 4to, 9v, ll. 1-2) that long puzzled editors (Jón Þorkelsson 1865: xiii; *Hauks*: cxx-cxxi;

The passage about the cross, however, is indebted to another sermon by Ælfric, the *Exaltatio Sanctae Crucis* (ll. 143-147):

We sceolan on ælcne timan and on ælcere styringe gebletsian us sylfe mid soðum geleafan; and mid rode-tacne þa reðan aflian; for ðan þe se reða deofol wearð þurh ða rode ofer-swiðed and heo is ure sige-beacn ongean þone sceocan á (Skeat 1881: 374).

[We shall on every occasion and in every trouble cross ourselves with true faith, and with the sign of the Cross put to flight the fierce ones, for that fierce devil was overcome through the rood, and it is ever our beacon of victory against the devil] (Skeat 1881: 375).

Despite the Old Norse translation's relative adherence to the model in this passage, the detail of the cross in the devil's mouth does not come from Ælfric, and Frankis suggested that «the ON writer could perhaps have arrived at this phrase by working independently from a Latin source» (2016: 76). The Latin source is unidentified, but the detail seems relatively common in contemporary iconography (see Appendix: figures 2, 3, 4) and might have originated in the Augustinian allegory of the devil captured by Christ's divinity like a fish on the hook (Scott-Macnab 2015). For instance, this specific Augustinian image exerted its influence on the description of Christ's harrowing of Hell in *Niðrstigningar saga*, an Old Norse translation of the *Descensus Christi ad inferos* section of *Evangelium Nicodemi*:

En þá er hann kom ok hugðizk mundu gleypa Jesum ok hafa hann með sér, þá beit ǫngull guðdómsins hann, en krossmarkit fell á hann ofan, ok varð hann svá veiddr sem fiskr á ǫngli, eðr mús undir tréketti, eðr melrakki í gildru, eptir því sem fyrir var spát. (Bullitta 2017: 141)

[But when he [the Devil] came there and thought he could swallow Jesus and carry Him away, the hook of divinity bit him, and the sign of the cross fell down on him, and he was caught like a fish on a fishhook, a mouse in a mousetrap, or an arctic fox in a snare, according to what was previously prophesied.] (Bullitta 2017: 162)

The Old Norse translation, likely dating to the last quarter of the twelfth century, shows evidence of influence from the Victorine reception of Augustine's homiletic writings, as demonstrated by Bullitta (2017: 86-95; 2023). While the Cross is not literally used as a prop in the devil's mouth in this text, it does play a role in his defeat (*en krossmarkit fell á hann ofan* 'and the sign of the cross fell upon him'). In Augustine's simile, the image operates on a purely allegorical

Reichborn-Kjennerud 1934: 144). On the codicological aspects of *Hauksbók*, see: Ashman-Rowe (2008).

level: Christ’s divinity “functions” as the hook, while his humanity serves as the bait. However, a more literal interpretation of the Augustinian trope might have suggested that, because the devil attempted to swallow Christ while on the Cross, the latter remained lodged in his mouth like a hook. Like *Niðrstigningar saga*, the Old Norse translations of Ælfric found in *Hauksbók* are generally considered to originate from the earliest period of vernacular literacy in Norway and Iceland, with most scholars favoring a date before *c.* 1200 (*Hauks*: cxx; Lombardi 2006: 594; Frankis 2016: 31-39, 89) or, possibly, shortly later (Ferrari 2012: 1-3)¹⁶. In the thirteenth-century *Duggals leiðsla*, a translation of the *Visio Tnugdali*, one of the most influential medieval visions of hell, the term *sparri* occurs in the description of the infernal beast Acheron, who devours the sinners of avarice and whose mouth is held open by two giants:

En í munnum stóðu tveir jǫtnar, ok horfði niður höfuðit á qðrum ok stóð á tǫnnum hins neðra gómsins, enn í móti því þá horfði höfuð annars upp undir tenn hins efra gómsins, enn iljar hans stóðu á inum neðrum tǫnnum. Ok með þessum hætti vóru þeir sem *sparrar* eða stolpar í munnum ok gerðu þrjú garðshlið á munnum. (Cahill 183: 32-33)

[And two giants stood in the mouth, and the head of the first one looked down and stood on the teeth of the lower palate, and, against that, the head of the other looked up, under the teeth of the upper palate, and the soles of his feet stood on the lower teeth. And in this way, they were like *spars* or posts, in the mouth and created three gateways in the mouth.]

Although composed considerably later than *Geisli*, likely during the reign of Hákon gamli Hákonarson (1217-1263), this text testifies to a long-lasting tradition of associating the notion of a *góm-sparri* with infernal and monstrous creatures. More relevant to our discussion of the *Geisli* kenning, however, is the explicit mention of the cross in the devil’s mouth in the *Hauksbók* sermon, which bears witness to the theological background that could have plausibly fostered a typological interpretation of Fenrir’s binding. This parallel reinforces Males’ hypothesis concerning the typological dimension of Einarr Skúlason’s kenning, in which the sword of Óláfr, through layers of allusion and interpretation, ultimately functions as a typological analogue to Christ’s Cross.

¹⁶ Scholars have mostly focused on the date of the sermon called *Um það hvaðan ótrú hófsk* (‘On the origin of idolatry’), an Old Norse translation of Ælfric’s *De falsiis diis*, immediately preceding the *Hér segir* in *Hauksbók*. A *terminus post quem* for its composition is the reference to Peter Comestor’s *Historia Scholastica*, which was completed *c.* 1173 (*Hauks*: cxx; 159). Conclusive evidence for a *terminus ante quem* remains scarce and, despite the large scholarly consensus for a date around *c.* 1200, a later date cannot be entirely excluded (Wellendorf 2018: 44).

7. Encircling the World

Einarr's interpretation of Fenrir's binding as a transfiguration of the devil's impairment finds a conceptual parallel in the Christian allegorical reading of Þórr's fishing of the Miðgarðsormr. Old Norse Christian learning readily equated this episode with the overcoming of the Biblical Leviathan, whom Christian exegesis had long identified as the fiendish dragon of Revelation¹⁷. The use of the name Miðgarðsormr in *Niðrstigningarsaga* further illustrates this connection:

Sá inn ríksti allvaldr leit þá til Jórsalaborgar ok mælti: “Gildra sú er at Jórsolum er gǫr verði Miðgarðsormi at skaða.” Hann fal þá ǫngul, þann er horvinn var agni ok eigi sjá mátti, í æzlinu, því er í gildiruna var lagit, ok svá vaðinn gat hann fólgit, svát eigi of mátti sjá. (Bullitta 2017: 139-140)

[Then He, the most powerful supreme ruler, looked towards Jerusalem and said: “May the trap that is made in Jerusalem harm the Midgard Serpent.” He then lowered a hook, in which was enclosed a bait that could not be seen into the carrion that was laid in the trap and, done that, He concealed it in such a way that it could not be seen.] (Bullitta 2017: 161)

The connection between the tail-biting serpent fished by Þórr and the fiendish Leviathan is particularly evident in the *Icelandic Homily Book* (c. 1200), where the compound *Miðgarðar* [sic] *ormr* figures as a gloss superscripted above the name “Leviathan” (Males 2022: 181-182) within a well-known sermon on the Resurrection of the Lord (*Upprisa dróttins*), a translation of Gregory the Great's *Homilia XXV in Evangelia*¹⁸. These texts demonstrate that, in the second half of the twelfth century, Norse intellectuals were actively and rather systematically reinterpreting their indigenous traditions, providing theologically significant explanations for figures and tales from the pagan world and aligning them with Christian learning.

Interestingly, *Geisli* features a Christian appropriation involving the very episode of Þórr fishing for the Miðgarðsormr, found in a passage attributed to the ninth-century skald Bragi Boddason. Sts 14-17 of *Geisli* describe Óláfr's ascent to Heaven following his death at Stiklastaðir. Just before falling in battle, Óláfr sees “a beautiful ladder ascending from earth to heaven” (*Geisli*, st 15, ll. 5-8), enabling his easy ascent into God's *himinríki* (‘heavenly kingdom’)¹⁹:

¹⁷ This topic has been object of much scholarly interest: Turville-Petre (1953: 126-128); Gschwantler 1968; Marchand 1975; Meulengracht-Sørensen 1986; Bullitta 2014; 2023; Males 2022.

¹⁸ Stockholm, Kungliga biblioteket, Holm. Perg. 15 4to, fol. 35v. See the discussion in Bullitta (2017: 78-79).

¹⁹ Óláfr's vision is reminiscent of the episode of Jacob's Ladder in the book of Genesis, typologically equated to Christ's Cross (Chase, *SkP* 7: 19-20).

Ok hagliga hugðisk
 hrøkkviseiðs ins dökkva
 lyngs í lopt upp ganga
 látrs stríðandi síðan.
 Lét, sá's landfolks gætir,
 líknframr himinríki
 umgeypnandi opnask
 alls heims fyr gram snjóllum.
 (*Geisli* 16, ed. M. Chase, *SkP* 7: 20-21)

[And it seemed to the fighter of the lair of the dark coiling pollack of the heather [SNAKE > GOLD > ÓLÁFR] that he could easily go up in the air, then. The one who protects the people of the country, the outstandingly merciful clutcher of the whole world [GOD], caused the kingdom of heaven to open before the clever king.]

In the second *helmingr* of this stanza, a new kenning-type for God is attested for the first time: *alls heims umgeypnandi* ('the encompasser, the one who holds in his hand the entire world'). The form *umgeypnandi* ('clutcher') is the present participle of a denominal verb from *gaupn* (f. 'cupped hand, hand's palm'). As Martin Chase notes, the kenning might have been inspired by the line *in manu eius fines terrae* ('in his hands are all the ends of the earth') from Psalm 94: 4 (*SkP* 7: 20-21). However, in light of strong skaldic echoes in the first *helmingr*, the kenning acquires additional layers of meaning. The first half-stanza features the long kenning *stríðandi látrs hrøkkviseiðs ins dökkva* ('the fighter of the lair of the dark coiling pollack of the heather'). Since "the lair of the snake" is a kenning for "gold", the periphrasis ultimately portrays Óláfr through the skaldic trope of the generous "gold-destroyer", traditionally applied to rulers. This stanza is somewhat reminiscent of a passage of Þórarinn Loftunga's *Glælognskviða* by (c. 1032), a funerary poem that was the first one to openly celebrate Óláfr's sanctity:

Hafði sér harðla ráðit
 Haralds sonr til himinríkis,
 áðr seimbrjótr at sætti varð [...].
 (*Glælognskviða* 4, ed. M. Townend, *SkP* 1: 869)

[The son of Haraldr [ÓLÁFR] had powerfully taken himself to the heavenly kingdom, before the treasure-breaker [RULER = ÓLÁFR] became a mediator [...] (*scil.* between God and men).]

However, the kennings *stríðandi látrs hrøkkviseiðs ins dökkva* and *umgeypnandi alls heims* also echo strongly the description of the Miðgarðsormr attributed to Bragi Boddason in *Skáldskaparmál*:

Bragi, *Þórr's fishing*, sts 3, 5

Hamri försk í hægri
hönd, þá's allra landa,
ægir Qflugbarða,
endiseiðs of kenndi.
Þá's forns Litar flotna
á fangboða ǫngli
hrökkviáll of hrokkinn
hekk Vǫlsunga drekku. (*SkP* 3: 49-51)

[The terrifier of Qflugbarði [GIANTESS > ÞÓRR] lifted the hammer in his right hand, when he recognised the border-pollack of all lands [MIDGARD'SORMR].
When the coiling eel of the drink of the Vǫlsungar [MIDGARD'SORMR] hung coiled up on the fishing hook of the wrestling-challenger of the followers of ancient Lit [ÞÓRR].]

Einarr Skúlaon, *Geisli*, st. 16

Ok hagliga hugðisk
hrökkviseiðs ins dökkva
lyngs í lopt upp ganga
látrs stríðandi síðan.
Lét, sá's landfolks gætir,
líknframr himinríki
umgeypnandi opnask
alls heims fyr gram snjóllum.

[And it seemed to the fighter of the lair of the dark coiling pollack of the heather [SNAKE > GOLD > ÓLÁFR] that he could easily go up in the air, then. The one who protects the people of the country, the outstandingly merciful clutcher of the whole world [GOD], caused the kingdom of heaven to open before the clever king.]

Here, the echoing involves appropriation of key lexical items from Bragi's kennings for the Miðgarðsormr: *allra landa endi-seiðr* ('the border-pollack of all lands', *i.e.* "the fish that is the border of all lands") and *hrökkvi-áll* ('coiling eel'). For an audience acquainted with this canonical text, the Óláfr-kennung *stríðandi* [...] *hrökkviseiðs ins dökkva* ('the fighter [...] of the dark coiling pollack') would have inevitably evoked Bragi's description of Þórr. In turn, the expression *umgeypnandi alls heims* reflects the conceptual framework of the Miðgarðsormr-kennung *allra landa endi-seiðr*. Lexical and structural elements of Bragi's kennings are thus recombined to describe Saint Óláfr and God, the latter being the *real* encompasser of all creation. This innovative kenning type proved immediately influential and was promptly imitated by later skalds²⁰. However, in this first occurrence, its structural and lexical composition seems heavily influenced by a pagan poem, illustrating a dynamic of *Kontrastimitation*.

Indeed, Einarr appears to have deliberately selected passages of the source-texts imbued with strong pagan sentiments, repurposing them to designate objects of the true faith. The title *harri* ('lord') is transferred from Óðinn to Christ, while the futile sacrifices offered to the pagan deities provide a strident contrast to the self-sacrifice of the Son of God. The sword placed in the mouth of Fenrir, like

²⁰ Einarr's kenning is imitated twice by Gamli kanóki in *Harmsól*, in st. 29: *skringeypnandi skýstalls* ('encompasser of the shrine of the cloud-ground [SKY > WORLD > GOD]'), and in st. 64: *heimspennir* ('world-clasper') and generalized in later poems (Attwood 1994: 228-230).

Christ's cross in the devil's mouth, becomes Saint Óláfr's sword, thereby reinforcing the typological reading of the king's life against the *exemplum Christi*, as programmatically outlined in the poem's opening. Finally, words once used to describe the Miðgarðsormr / Leviathan are recast into kennings for Saint Óláfr and for God, whose embrace gently encompasses the creation. As suggested in previous scholarship, this operation, far from a simple "accommodation" of pagan diction, exhibits traits of exegetical thought. Pagan eschatological narratives and the associated symbols are allegorically interpreted as a prefiguration of Christ's triumph over the forces of evil. In particular, the radical subversion of an impious entity into a salvific one is reminiscent of the exegetical principle known as Augustinian chiasm, an audacious allegorical juxtaposition, whose «full force depends very much on the precise nature of the reversal» (Satran 2004: 358). This allegorical approach is typical, for instance, of the aforementioned *Niðrstigningar saga*, where the deceiver *par excellence*, the devil, is finally deceived by Christ (Satran 2004; Bullitta 2023: 190-191). The chiasmic principle seems to apply in all the examined instances, where an impious pagan-devilish entity is contrasted with a salvific counterpoint: Óðinn / Christ; Fenrir's *gómssparri* / Óláfr's sword; Miðgarðsormr / God. As evidenced by homiletic and scriptural translations from the second half of the twelfth century, Norse intellectuals of this era were engaging in an allegorical reading of their pagan heritage. The traces of exegetical activity detected in *Geisli* may indeed reflect a tendency typical of the earliest phase of Old Norse literacy (c. 1150-1200), where the vernacular response to foreign literary genres was expressed in verse rather than in prose (Guðrún Nordal 2001b; Males forthcoming).

Around the same time in which Einarr composed *Geisli*, an intense exegetical activity based on the reprise of Augustine's writings flourished in the works of the masters of the Paris school of theology, most notably Hugh of Saint Victor, Peter the Lombard and Peter Comestor (Callus 1941: 170-172; Smalley 1978: 83-242). Their doctrines quickly found their way to Scandinavia, particularly to the cathedral schools, influencing the composition of Old Norse vernacular works (Bullitta 2014; 2023; 2024). While the nature of Einarr's readings makes pinpointing the precise source of his exegetical insights difficult, his poem is declaredly inspired by the activity of those "excellent men" (*framir*) who study the Scriptures, as stated in the opening section of *Geisli*:

Veitti dýrðar dróttinn
 dáðvandr gjafar anda
 (mól kynnask þau) mönnum
 máttigs (*framir vátta*). (*Geisli* 6, ed. M. Chase, *SkP* 7: 11-12)

[The carefully-acting lord of glory [GOD] gave to men the gifts of the mighty spirit;
 excellent men study those sayings of witnesses [SCRIPTURES].]

In the following stanza, Einarr adds: *menn nemi mól, sem innik | mín [...]* ('may men understand my words, as I tell them')²¹. This remark could be interpreted as the expression either of a conventional topos of humility or of genuine concern. As an experienced skald, Einarr was well aware that not all audiences would appreciate the obscure style of *dróttkvætt* verse²². However, his allusive style suggests that he relied on the skaldic competence of at least some of his listeners and, perhaps, this remark could be equally read as a hint to the layered messages contained in *Geisli's* lines and kennings. Arguably, the exegetical activity of discerning the true, spiritual meaning of things beyond the deceptive veil of the literal sense (Smalley 1978: 1) chimes well with the enigmatic nature of skaldic poetics, where true meanings are "hidden in secrets or in the poetic art", as declared by the god Bragi in *Skáldskaparmál* (*Vér felum í rínum eða í skáldskap*, Faulkes 1998, I: 3). As the examples above demonstrate, Einarr Skúlaason was well-versed in both.

8. Conclusions

In the course of the twelfth century, «the conflict between the Christian religion of the poets and the pagan mythic elements inherent in the traditional poetic diction was fully resolved» (Guðrún Nordal 2001a: 7). The case studies examined above suggest that this resolution was underpinned not by a purely grammatical approach, but that an exegetical principle operated in unison with it. While Einarr Skúlaason's stylistic exercises most clearly demonstrate the imitation of earlier poets, this study has argued that a more subtle yet significant dialogue with the vernacular tradition persists in his religious verse. Through appropriative allusion, canonical *loci* are re-semanticized, in an operation that is both literary and hermeneutical. As Roberts observes, «every example of intertextuality potentially entails a process definable in terms of metaphor and exegesis» (2004: 48). In the "skaldic exegeses" of *Geisli*, two distinctive aspects of skaldic poetics, intertextual allusion and metaphor, are for the first time enrolled in the service of Christian learning. If taken in isolation, each of the three instances of poetic allusion examined above might appear too elusive to support claims of exegetical activity in *Geisli*. Their cumulative effect, however, coupled with Einarr's systematic use of allusive imitation observed in other sections of his work, strengthens the argument and their occurrence provides an early poetic parallel to analogous exegetical couplings found in roughly contemporary homiletic texts. Moreover, the techniques

²¹ Einarr Skúlaason, *Geisli*, st. 7, ed. by Martin Chase (*SkP* 7: 12-13).

²² According to *Knýtlinga saga*, Einarr's poetic ingenuity was rather coldly received at the Danish court of Sveinn sviðandi (*ÍF* 35: 275; Wellendorf 2017: 125).

of imitation-and-distancing observed in this article recall dynamics typical of the first Christian epics in Latin by Juvencus, Sedulius, and Arator. A particularly fitting parallel is provided by the intertextual strategy of *Kontrastimitation*, in which «the alluding poet follows or cites a predecessor closely in such a way as to signal a major alteration of significance» (Green 2006: 63; Thraede 1962). There is ample evidence of the centrality of these early Christian epics in the school curriculum of Anglo-Saxon England, where they served as the primary introduction to both devotional reading and Latin versification (Lapidge 2006; McBrine 2017: 4; 211-214). While their presence in the North is less well documented, their canonical status and wide circulation suggest that they might have plausibly served as concrete literary models for Einarr Skúlason's poetic endeavours. This topic warrants further investigation; for now, it may suffice to say that late-antique Christian poets provide an interesting parallel, as they faced similar challenges in signaling their appropriation of a prestigious genre, whose cultural underpinnings were strongly at odds with the new faith's content and message. A limiting factor in the evaluation of Einarr's methods is our lack of knowledge about his formal education. Given the nature of his exegetical approach, the resort to seemingly Augustinian tropes may suggest contacts with the strand of studies emanating from the Parisian school of St Victor, where some contemporary Icelanders and several Norwegians received their education (Bullitta 2014: 231-236 and the relative appendices: 237-245). However, as the school was founded in 1110 and Einarr had likely completed his studies before joining Sigurður jórsalafari on his pilgrimage to the Holy Lands, the Victorines' influence was more likely later and indirect, possibly coming via Norway. Einarr Skúlason operated in an ecclesiastical network saturated with Victorine theology and texts, and his position as a poet-priest at the royal court in the 1150s would have facilitated exposure to Parisian exegetical methods (Bullitta 2024: 225). As the first known skald to engage in the activity of coupling pagan myths with Christian meanings, Einarr emerges as a "pioneer", whose work significantly influenced not only the style of religious skaldic verse but also the learned reception of early vernacular poetry. His mappings reflect a contemporary interest in the indigenous pre-Christian lore of the North, partly based on the widespread medieval, and ultimately Pauline, conviction that pagans possessed some understanding of the world, albeit imperfect and fallacious (Males 2013: 112-113; Wellendorf 2018: 7). This attitude would later inform the antiquarian approach of his most famous relative, Snorri Sturluson (Faulkes 2005: xxvi-xxvii; 4). Standing «on the threshold of a new, exciting era» (2003: 8), Einarr Skúlason, this semi-unknown Janus figure, might have contributed to shaping the perception of the vernacular poetic heritage more deeply and subtly than scholars have so far realized.

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Fig. 2. The Harrowing of Hell, Psalter of Eleanor of Aquitaine, Normandy, c. 1185 (KB 76 F 13, 24v, Koninklijke Bibliotheek, National Library of the Netherlands). Source: <<https://galerij.kb.nl/kb.html#/en/psalter/page/26/zoom/2/lat/-58.63121664342478/lng/-140.625>>.

Fig. 3. The Harrowing of Hell, *Illustrated Vita Christi*, Northern Anglia, York, c. 1190-1200 (Ms. 101, fol 82v, Collection of The J. Paul Getty Museum). Source: <<https://www.getty.edu/art/collection/object/109CRQ>>.

Fig. 4. The Harrowing of Hell and Noli Me Tangere, *Munich Golden Psalter*, England, Gloucester (?), c. 1200-1225 (Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, Clm 835, f. 59). Source: <http://daten.digitale-sammlungen.de/bsb00012920/image_59>.